

Jaqqot5 tutorials

Jaqqot 5: How to manage and use organisations

USE:	How to manage and use organisations
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INTRODUCTION

Jaqpot 5 is a user-friendly web-based e-infrastructure that allows model developers to deploy their predictive models and share them through the web. The Jaqpot 5 GUI directs the model developers to further document their models in a way that can be easily understood and used by end-users with little or no experience on machine learning and statistical analysis. The GUI also allows the end-users to apply the models on their own data for validation and/or prediction purposes and the results are collected and visualised in automatically generated tables, graphs and reports. All major machine learning and statistical data-driven algorithms are supported in Jaqpot 5, by integrating popular libraries such as the Python Scikit-learn and the R Caret libraries. Jaqpot 5 has been designed as a generic modelling and machine learning web platform, but particular emphasis is given on serving the needs of the chemo/bio/nano/pharma/ communities by integrating QSAR, biokinetics, dose-response and read-across models. Jaqpot 5 has been developed by the [Unit of Process Control and Informatics](#) in the School of Chemical Engineering at the National Technical University of Athens.

This document provides a tutorial on how to create and manage organisations in Jaqpot5. The resource has been made available at <https://accounts.jaqpot.org/>. Detailed documentation is available at: <https://www.jaqpot.org/>

HOW TO MANAGE AND USE ORGANISATIONS

An important feature introduced in Jaqpot 5 is the concept of organisations, i.e. virtual groups for sharing resources, i.e. datasets and models. A Jaqpot user can create his own organisations, where he can invite colleagues and partners. The size of an organisation can range from a small one consisting of only a few members working on a collaborative modelling project. to a much larger one hosting all the resources of a H2020 research project, a laboratory, or a University department.

A Jaqpot 5 user can use and manage organisations by clicking on the “account” icon located on the top-right part of the screen (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Access the accounts application from Jaqpot.

The user is transferred to the Jaqpot accounts landing page and he is prompted to click on the “Login” button (Figure 2)

Figure 2. The Jaqpot accounts landing page.

The user enters the Jaqpot credentials. The basic page in the Jaqpot accounts application opens up, where the user can enter his personal information (Figure 3). The user can see a list of organisations where he is a member by clicking on the drop down menu on the bottom of the page (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Basic page of the Jaqpot accounts application

The screenshot shows a user profile interface. On the left, there is a circular profile picture of a network graph, the text "Welcome, Pantelis Karatzas", and an "About" button with a pencil icon. The main content area is divided into three sections: "Personal info" (collapsed), "Organizations" (expanded), and "Domains" (collapsed). The "Organizations" section is titled "Member of" and lists the following organizations: NanoCommons, Lab of Process Control and Informatics, KoolAndTheGand, NanoSolveIT, LamaRed (with a red profile picture icon), My New, PDB_Organization, TestAnother!, and NanoSolveit. A pink arrow button is located at the bottom right of the organizations list.

Organizations	Member of
NanoCommons	
Lab of Process Control and Informatics	
KoolAndTheGand	
NanoSolveIT	
LamaRed	
My New	
PDB_Organization	
TestAnother!	
NanoSolveit	

Figure 4. List of organizations

By clicking on one of the organizations, the application opens the specific organization page (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Organization page.

The *Users* tab opens the list with the members of the organisation and the contact e-mails (Figure 5). The creator of the organisation and other administrators can invite other Jaqpot5 users in the organisation by clicking on the “invite” button. A dialog allows the administrator to add the new member email and a message that will follow the invitation. Also administrators can add other users as administrators.

Figure 6. The Users tab

The Admins Tab shows all the administrators of an organization (Figure 7)

Figure 7. Organization Admins tab.

A new organisation can be created by clicking the *CREATE ORGANIZATION* button in the organizations tab (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Creating a new organisation.

The user will be prompted to a page where he adds the name for the new organisation (Figure 9).

The image shows a dialog box with the title "Give organizations name". Inside the dialog, there is a text input field with the placeholder text "Organizations name" and a small icon of a grid on the right side. Below the input field, there is a validation message: "Must be at least three characters long". At the bottom right of the dialog, there are two buttons: "Cancel" and a button with a plus sign and the text "Add".

Figure 9. Entering the name for the new organisation.

When a Jaqpot user is invited to become a member of an organisation he receives a notification which can be viewed by clicking on the bell icon on the top of the screen (Figure 10).

Figure 10. The notification button.

A window pops-up where the user can either accept or decline the invitation (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Responding to an invitation to become a member of an organisation.

When a user is a member of an organisation, he can share his resources (datasets, models) with the members of the organisation (for more details read the tutorial on **how to deploy a predictive model using the jaqpotpy library**) and he can test and use resources shared by other members of the organisation (For more information read the tutorial on **how to access and use an existing predictive model**).

Support

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